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NUMERICAL MODELING OF PROBLEMS OF A NONLINEAR MODEL OF SALT TRANSFER IN AN INHOMOGENEOUS MEDIUM WITH ABSORPTION AND WITH A SOURCE

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ABSTRACT: This article presents the results of calculations of the Cauchy problem for a quasilinear parabolic equation describing a nonlinear model of salt transfer in an inhomogeneous medium with absorption and with a source. Numerical schemes, algorithms and programs have been developed using the universal mathematical package Mathcad. Numerical schemes, methods of linearization, methods of solution and stability of the method for the filtration process in an inhomogeneous medium with absorption or a source for the cases $N = 1$ and $N = 2$.

Keywords: boundary condition, Picard method, special method, Newton's method, the Pisman - Rockford scheme.

INTRODUCTION. Numerical schemes and methods of solution

Consider in the area $\Omega = \{(t, x) : 0 < t < T, 0 < x < b\}$ the equation

$$Lu \equiv -u_t + \nabla \cdot (|x|^m K(u) \nabla u) + \varepsilon \gamma(t, x) Q(u) = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N \quad (1)$$

with initial and boundary conditions

$$u(0, x) = \psi(x) \geq 0, \quad 0 \leq x \leq b, \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{cases} u(t, 0) = \varphi_1(t) > 0 \\ u(t, b) = \varphi_2(t) = 0 \end{cases}, \quad t \in [0, T], \quad (3)$$

which in the case of degenerating is equivalent to the Cauchy problem with a finite initial function $u_0(x) \geq 0, |x| \geq 1 > 0 \dots$

Here $K(u) = u^\sigma$, $Q(u) = u^\beta$ - fairly smooth functions, $m \neq 0$, $0 < \gamma(t, x) \in C(0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^N$, $\varepsilon = \pm 1 \dots$

First, consider the one-dimensional case ($N = 1$).

IN $\bar{\Omega}$ build a uniform mesh $\bar{\omega}_h$ on x step by step h :

$$\bar{\omega}_h = \{x_i = ih, \quad h > 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n, \quad hn = b\},$$

and time grid

$$\bar{\omega}_\tau = \{t_j = j\tau, \quad \tau > 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m, \quad \tau m = T\}, \quad T > 0 \dots$$

We replace problem (1) - (3), using the balance method, by an implicit difference scheme and obtain a difference problem with an error $O(h^2 + \tau)$:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} \left[|x_{i+1}|^m a_{i+1}(y^{j+1}) (y_{i+1}^{j+1} - y_i^{j+1}) - |x_i|^m a_i(y^{j+1}) (y_i^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1}) \right] + \\ \quad + \varepsilon \gamma(t_j, x_i) b_i(y^{j+1}), & i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1; \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1, \\ y_i^0 = u_0(x_i), & i = 0, 1, \dots, n, \\ y_0^j = \varphi_1(t_j), & j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \\ y_n^j = \varphi_2(t_j), & j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $b_i(y^{j+1}) = (y_i^{j+1})^\beta$ and to calculate $a(y)$ one of the following formulas is used

$$\begin{aligned} \text{but) } a_i(y) &= K \left(\frac{y_{i-1} + y_i}{2} \right), \\ \text{b) } a_i(y) &= \frac{K(y_{i-1}) + K(y_i)}{2} \dots \end{aligned}$$

The system of algebraic equations (4) is nonlinear with respect to $y^{j+1} \dots$

To solve a system of nonlinear equations, we apply various iterative methods and obtain:

$$\frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} \left[(|x_{i+1}|)^m a_{i+1} \left(y^{j+1} \right) \left(y_{i+1}^{j+1} - y_i^{j+1} \right) - (|x_i|)^m a_i \left(y^{j+1} \right) \left(y_i^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1} \right) \right] + \varepsilon \gamma(t_j, x_i) b_i(y^{j+1}) \quad (5)$$

where $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots \dots$

one) $b_i(y^{j+1}) = \left(y_i^s \right)^\beta$ - the Picard method,

2) $b_i(y^{j+1}) = y_i^{s+1} \left(y_i^s \right)^{\beta-1}$ - a special method,

3) $b_i(y^{j+1}) = \left(y_i^s \right)^\beta + \beta \left(y_i^s \right)^{\beta-1} \left(y_i^{s+1} - y_i^s \right)$ - Newton's method.

Relatively y_i^{s+1} difference scheme (5) is linear. As an initial iteration for y_i^{s+1} taken y from the previous time step: $y_i^{j+1} = y_i^j \dots$ When counting according to an iterative scheme, the iteration accuracy is specified and the process continues until the condition

$$\max_{0 \leq i \leq n} \left| y_i^{s+1} - y_i^s \right| < \varepsilon \dots$$

Comment. In all numerical calculations, we assumed $\varepsilon = 10^{-3} \dots$

In (5), we introduce the notation

1) for the Picard method

$$A_i^s = \frac{\tau \cdot (|x_{i-1}|)^m}{h^2} \left(\frac{y_i^{j+1} + y_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2} \right)^\sigma, \quad B_i^s = \frac{\tau \cdot (|x_{i+1}|)^m}{h^2} \left(\frac{y_{i+1}^{j+1} + y_i^{j+1}}{2} \right)^\sigma,$$

$$C_i^s = A_i^s + B_i^s + 1, \quad F_i^s = y_i^s + \varepsilon \tau \cdot \gamma(t_j, x_i) \left(y_i^{j+1} \right)^\beta, \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \dots$$

2) for a special method

$$A_i^s = \frac{\tau \cdot (|x_{i-1}|)^m}{h^2} \left(\frac{y_i^{j+1} + y_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2} \right)^\sigma, \quad B_i^s = \frac{\tau \cdot (|x_{i+1}|)^m}{h^2} \left(\frac{y_{i+1}^{j+1} + y_i^{j+1}}{2} \right)^\sigma,$$

$$C_i^s = A_i^s + B_i^s + 1 - \varepsilon \tau \cdot \gamma(t_j, x_i) \left(y_i^{j+1} \right)^{\beta-1}, \quad F_i^s = y_i^{j+1}, \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \dots$$

3) for Newton's method

$$A_i^s = \frac{\tau \cdot (|x_{i-1}|)^m}{h^2} \left(\frac{y_i^{j+1} + y_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2} \right)^\sigma, \quad B_i^s = \frac{\tau \cdot (|x_{i+1}|)^m}{h^2} \left(\frac{y_{i+1}^{j+1} + y_i^{j+1}}{2} \right)^\sigma,$$

$$C_i^s = A_i^s + B_i^s + 1 - \varepsilon \tau \cdot \gamma(t_j, x_i) \left(y_i^{j+1} \right)^{\beta-1}, \quad F_i^s = y_i^s + \varepsilon \tau \cdot \gamma(t_j, x_i) \left[\left(y_i^{j+1} \right)^\beta - \beta \left(y_i^{j+1} \right)^\beta \right], \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, n \dots$$

Let us agree on the following notation

$$y^j = y, \quad y^{j+1} = \bar{y} \dots$$

The difference equation can be written as

$$A_i^s \bar{y}_{i-1}^{s+1} - C_i^s \bar{y}_i^{s+1} + B_i^s \bar{y}_{i+1}^{s+1} = -F_i^s, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1 \dots \quad (6)$$

To numerically solve the system of equations (6), the sweep method is used. From the boundary conditions from (4) we have

$$\bar{y}_0 = \varphi_1(t_{j+1}), \quad \bar{y}_n = \varphi_2(t_{j+1}) \dots$$

Let be

$$\bar{y}_i = \alpha_i (\beta_i + \bar{y}_{i+1}) \tag{7}$$

where α_i, β_i are still unknown coefficients [1].

The quantities α_i, β_i is found as follows:

Putting (7) in the notation i and $i-1$ points in the equation (6)

$$(A_i - C_i \alpha_i + B_i \alpha_{i-1} \alpha_i) \cdot \bar{y}_{i+1} + (-C_i \alpha_i \beta_i + B_i \alpha_{i-1} \beta_{i-1} + B_i \alpha_{i-1} \alpha_i \beta_i + F_i) = 0,$$

equality (6) will hold if we require

$$\begin{cases} A_i - C_i \alpha_i + B_i \alpha_{i-1} \alpha_i = 0 \\ -C_i \alpha_i \beta_i + B_i \alpha_{i-1} \beta_{i-1} + B_i \alpha_{i-1} \alpha_i \beta_i + F_i = 0 \end{cases} \dots$$

From here we find the running coefficients α_i, β_i :

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_i = \frac{A_i}{C_i - \alpha_{i-1} B_i} \\ \beta_i = \frac{B_i \alpha_{i-1} \beta_{i-1} + F_i}{A_i} \end{cases}, i = \overline{2, n} \dots \tag{8}$$

The quantities α_1, β_1 are found from (7) and (6) for $i = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{y}_1 &= \alpha_1 (\beta_1 + y_2), \\ \bar{y}_1 &= \frac{A_1 \bar{y}_2 + B_1 \bar{y}_0 + F_1}{C_1} \dots \end{aligned}$$

From here

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_1 = \frac{A_1}{C_1} \\ \beta_1 = \frac{B_1 \varphi_1 + F_1}{A_1} \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

Thus, the coefficients are found $\alpha_i, \beta_i \quad i = \overline{1, n} \dots$

The solution to system (4) is found by the recurrent formula (7). Meaning $\bar{y}_n$ we obtain from the boundary condition (4)

$$\begin{cases} \bar{y}_n = \varphi_2 \\ \bar{y}_{n-1} = \alpha_{n-1} (\beta_{n-1} + \bar{y}_n) \\ \vdots \\ \bar{y}_i = \alpha_i (\beta_i + \bar{y}_{i+1}) \\ \vdots \end{cases} \dots \tag{10}$$

To apply the sweep method, it suffices to require that the coefficients of system (6) satisfy the condition ([2])

$$A_i \neq 0, \quad B_i \neq 0, \quad |C_i| \geq |A_i| + |B_i|, \quad i = \overline{1, n} \dots \tag{11}$$

For the iterative scheme (5), the sweep method is stable and gives a unique solution.

Conclusion

The use of modern computer systems to solve the problems of mathematical physics, in particular for the problem of the process of moisture and salt transfer in soils based on models of the movement of multicomponent impurities in porous media has become the most urgent task. The study of various properties of auto-model (one-dimensional) equations, simpler compared to multidimensional equations in partial derivatives, is a relatively easy task and therefore equations of this kind are amenable to more detailed analysis. When solving a two-dimensional problem, the method of variable directions is used, i.e., calculations are carried out according to the Pisman - Rockford scheme. The problem was considered in a one-dimensional and two-dimensional area and, respectively, the graphical results are shown in two-dimensional and three-dimensional space.

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